

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Triyandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol. XIV, Book. III -IV

JULY - DECEMBER 2022

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किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

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Dharma: The Bed Rock of Social Philosophy of Renaissance Thinkers of Kerala.

Rakesh. K¹

The word dharma comes from the verbal root ‘dhr’ which means to hold, to sustain, or to support. Thus dharma stands for the individual essence of objects or for the inner law by which they are sustained or supported. So often its meaning extends from individual objects to the entire universe. Thus dharma becomes the inner principle which sustains or holds together the entire universe. Another sense dharma implies not only moral virtues or duties, but the whole set of customs, laws, rules, rituals, religious beliefs and practices recognised as approved or settled in the society for the people to follow. It is by the observance of all these that the social fabric is sustained or held together. Through this paper I would like to highlight this aspect of dharma which was the basis of the social Philosophy of the Renaissance thinkers of Kerala.

Social conditions in Kerala during the latter part of 19th century and first part of 20th century were so pathetic. Caste and religion were tangled with men’s deepest psychic, cultural and economic concerns and were, therefore, a fundamental phenomenon of political life. Untouchability, superstition, social discrimination, irrational customs, social injustices, etc., were taking an upper hand in those days. To make social condition right social reformers like Agamananda, Ayyankali, Addul khader Maulavi, Brahmananda Sivayogi, Chattampi

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Swamikal, Sree Narayana Guru and Vagbhatananda were in the scene. Agamananda, Brahmananda sivayogi, Chattampi Swamikal, Sree Narayana Guru, Vagbhatananda were spiritual leaders as well as social reformers. Kerala renaissance movement was especially against the existing vulgar caste discrimination. Leaders of these movements were mainly against the evils existing on the basis of caste. They thought that through a solution to this major problem. Renaissance thinkers fought against this major social problem in the basis of dharma philosophy.

Chattampi Swamikal deserves a prominent place among the renaissance leaders of Kerala. He pervaded a new life and potency into Hinduism at a time when it was facing the threat of conversions from within its fold to the more vigorous faiths that came from abroad, i.e., Islam and Christianity. His activities achieved a large measure of success in stemming the wave of such conversions from Hinduism. He fought uncompromisingly against casteism of all kinds and eradicated all the evils practices that had crept into Hindu dharma. His main achievement as a social and religious reformer was that he could stimulate the social consciousness of the members of his own caste, i.e., the Nairs and make them fight against the social evils that had crept into their ranks. Though the Nairs belonged to the upper caste their position was inferior to the Namboothiri Brahmin in the society, the introduction of western education, the growth of the social consciousness among the other lower caste etc. contributed to the decline of the Nair dominance in the society of Kerala during the second half of the 19th century. It was in this background, the decline of the Nair dominance in the society of Kerala, the new generation of the Nairs raised their voice for reform. It was Chattampi Swamikal who initiated the social reform movement among the Nairs. He tried to put an end to the Brahmin dominance in the religious rites and ceremonies. Swami had to pass through a period when Brahmin domination was forcefully set. He was the first to revolt theoretically against the Brahmin domination and his arguments based on historical

facts destroyed existing authorities on which the unjust system was based. In his 'Pracheena Malayalam' he has demolished some of the traditional views of Kerala history on the basis of factual evidence. He believed that early Kerala society was based on the principles of social freedom and equality and that *chathurvarnya* was introduced by the Brahmins in order to substitute their own self-interest. He rejected the traditional story of the creation of Kerala by Parasurama as fictitious and false one concocted by the same class of Brahmins to perpetuate their hold in the society. By projecting the picture of an original casteless society in ancient Kerala and of the chaos shaped in it by the introduction of *chathurvarnya*, Chattampi Swamikal kindled social awareness among the people and gave an impetus to the socio-religious reform movement in Kerala.

At a period when the elite claimed that the study of Vedas was the monopoly of the Brahmins, Swami confidently argued that all such barriers in the realm of knowledge and thought were baseless and illogical. He effectively established this through his speeches, and writings. Swami by correctly interpreting the concerned Vedic texts established the eligibility of all, irrespective of caste or sex, for the study of teachings of Vedas. He argued that as food is essential for the existence and growth of the body, knowledge of God is essential for the existence and development of the spirit on its way to the supreme spirit. Denying the non-Brahmin the right to learn Vedas is like denying food him or her without which no one can exist. His vision of unity (*samadarsana*) was the outcome of his belief in and adherence to the Advaita principle that *Atman is Brahman*' each man is potentially divine; that all existence is one. So Swami argued that Vedic knowledge and temples should be open to all. He believed that spiritual knowledge is as much a substance needed to man as food is and so he dedicated himself to the task of making individuals ideal citizens by uplifting them spiritually.

The most important work that initiated religious reform in Kerala was Swami's 'Vedhadhikara Nirupanam.' It is an

introspection of Vedic texts dealing with social and religious rights and rites. It points out the misrepresentation to the Vedic texts incorporated by later interest groups who forbade the study of Vedas by lower caste people and women. Through it, Swami established the right of every man to learn and teach Vedas. In this work he exposes the absurdity of the centuries-old tradition of birth in high caste as a prerequisite for study of the Vedas and he firmly establishes that such study is appropriate for all who wish it. He held that those who have a desire to study them can do that according to their capacities without fear of incurring any sin on that account. He thought that the study of Vedas is essential for life and so learning and teaching them becomes everybody's right. In this work he has established the theoretical basis of the religious and social reforms he advocated. It is a unique appraisal of the principles of Vedanta. This has been rightly pointed out by A. Sreedhara Menon when he wrote, "In this challenge Swamikal shatters the myth of the Brahmin right on the monopoly of Vedic learning and asserted the right of every Hindu, irrespective of caste, to have free access to the treasures of Vedic lore (Nair and Sulochana Devi. N 364)." Until Swami's time in Kerala, studentship was considered the monopoly of Brahmins. The study of Vedas was prohibited to *Sudras* and women. While *Kshatriyas* and *Vaisyas* could study Vedas they also cannot teach them. Brahmins alone were entitled to the study and teachings of Veda. By quoting from the Vedas and srutis and by correctly interpreting the authentic texts, in *Vedadhikara Nirupanam*, Swami established the eligibility of all, irrespective of caste or sex, for the study and teachings of the Vedas. According to him, restricting the use of Vedas, which are the guide books of moksa, within a class is injustice. This unjust trend got established powerfully in Kerala and it was against this Swami launched his explosive ideas. Swami was filled a firm determination to break into the stronghold of orthodoxy and establish the right of everyone to study the Vedas. He was the first intellect who questioned the scriptural hegemony of Brahmins. Chattampi Swamikal

built up a value consciousness aimed at the regeneration of the existing social life of Kerala. The ideological components of his thought, distributed through his writings and disciples, were self-respect, rationalism, equality, women's freedom, nonviolence and humanism.

Bramanandha Swami Sivayogi was another prominent renaissance leader of Kerala. Sivayogi considered the caste system as a mere super-imposition. He advocated that “the equality of all human beings saying that the identity like religion, caste, family, native, nobility of birth etc., are all absorbed in childhood by association with particular group. They were not the order of God. They are all man's own creations. They were a threat to human life and bring only distress. It was a shame that it was man's quarrel over man that created distinctions. Caste and religion are difficulties to human thought. Creatures appear in different forms due to their distinguishing features. Hence they belong to different species. But no such difference of features is seen among human beings” (B. S. Sivayogi 13-14) . He visited villages and explained the ordinary masses the need for giving up superstitions. His material ideology had great appeal to the people. Sivayogi discloses the uselessness of idol worship. He proved that idol worship is one of the most irrational things on solid basis of logic and sacred books of Hindus. Sivayogi asserts:

“The real temple of God is the human body
 God is within the heart of all human beings
 So we should dissolve our mind in that God
 To seek the eternal pleasure in life” (Sivayogi 9)

There is no God who provides wealth and skill but is our own mind which creates wealth. Any effort without the control of mind would become futile to achieve this. He said ignorance of the people which caused the fight for religion and caste. Atheist, rationalist and humanists were attracted his ideas and philosophy. Sivayogi's aim was to reform the people and make them scientific and rational. He spread his idea through his speeches, advices and literary works. Sivayogi formulated

his system of thought, oriented towards socio-religious transformation. He always emphasized the importance of human mind and its transformation. Sivayogi negated all the arguments on the existence of God as described by different religions. Sivayogi questioned the divine belief determined by the purohitas. He has exposed that his aim was to unite all people who fight in the name of caste and religion. The religious scriptures and leaders produced the formation of caste and caste difference. According to Sivayogi, all beings are born from happiness and all desire happiness. So happiness or bliss is only true and inherent religion (Anandamatha) in the world.

Narayana Guru, the great renaissance leader, accepts Advaita as the metaphysical basis for man's practical concern in the world, devoted his whole life to showing the world that Advaita can be translated into action. He attempted to bring the true Advaitic teaching into the realm of practical life. It should be noted that in modern times several Hindu religious leaders have emphasized the practical application of Sankaracharya's Advaita Vedanta. Guru's teachings are not to be sought primarily in the words, spoken or written, but in his life and methods of work. Swami Dharma Theerthan described that "The underlying principles of his life and methods of work are the moral and the spiritual identity of the individuals as well as the communities' life and growth based on the oneness of all life, the identity of the laws which govern it, and the Supreme Unity of purpose. He puts these principles in the simple motto: One caste, One religion, One God" (Dharmateerthan 111). The Guru led a holy life of Vedantins who gives importance to the principle of unity, solidarity in practical life and to supreme synthesis, which is the goal of philosophical idealism. His advaitic vision was being translated every minute of his life into the fields that were beneficial to his fellowmen. He combined peacefulness of inner life with a rare capacity to turn out a large amount of useful work for the people with whom he came into contact. The guru's advaitism was not confined to the perceptual world alone. While he seemed to agree with Sankara in his arguments in favour of the supreme intellectual monism,

his divergence with his teacher became more marked when it came to applied Vedanta. The advaitism of the Guru did not stop with Religion. It came down to more concrete levels of human life and relations. His teachings echoed through the years after his samadhi.

These social reformers and their movements had profound influence in all Sections of Kerala society. This dilemma powered the emergence of Dalit agitations later under the charismatic leadership of Ayyankali. Emerging as the Dalit voice of rebellion in the later decades of the 19th century when Kerala was excited with dissenting voices against caste and social inequalities by the upwardly mobile middle class of the Ezhavas and Nairs, Ayyankali waged a spirited battle for bringing the Dalits, especially the Pulayas, on a par with the status of the domineering middle class. The Dalits were never considered as part of the public and were least represented in the public opinion to the extent that they, despite bearing the brunt of a lumpen exploitative system, were never in the picture in the discourses of reformation and social integration.

The spirit of Ayyankali's spontaneous revolt was his bold attempt to lay claim for, or to make a forceful entry into, the public space which he believed will enable the oppressed people to brave all forms of oppressions and brutalities. He organized a small band of revolutionary youths called 'Ayyankalippada' (M.Nissar and Kandaswamy). Ayyankali along with this group defied the most obvious points of caste discrimination and spearheaded an all-out war against all forms of exploitations. By bravely violating the caste rules which brazenly denied Dalits entry into public roads and marketplaces, this movement sought to subvert the symbolic world of Jati maryada true in the discourses of reformation and social integration.

Vagbhatananda was another renaissance leader. He fought against the evil customs, rituals and superstitious beliefs so as to make new light into the cast ridden society of Malabar. He strove hard in liberating the people from fetters of caste,

complicated customs, and concocted ritualistic traditions through speeches and writings. The first important literary composition of Vagbhatananda was Brahmasankirttanam and his important philosophical work Atmavidya. (The wisdom of soul) was published in the year 1925. The salient features of Advaita philosophies are set down in Atmavidya. This work also turned to be the manifesto of his organization, Atmavidyasangham. In the preface to Atmavidya Vagbhatananda explained the intention of writing this book. He argues that the treatment of our religion as good and others as bad is dangerous. The cardinal doctrine of all religious leaders is one and their statement of ethics and ideals have a universal form or identical vision. In the preface he also paid great tribute to Rajaram Mohan Roy and Propagation of his Brahma Dharma. The book contains description of spiritual social and moral principles to be practiced by human being throughout his/her life. The influence of Brahmanical texts like Bhagavat Gita, Kadopanishad and other books on Vedanta are evident in this book. He visualized a society which combines love, self-respect, liberty and equality. He says that 'Advaitatmavidya' is the way to oppose social evils. It is a thought for the excellence of individual and society. The book, Atmavidya was an open statement of the policies and functions of the socio-religious reform movement.

The philosophical perspective of Vagbhatananda had a strong base of Rationalism and moral values. He gave stress to the reconstruction of society. K. K. N. Kurup described that "In this politically charged and socially dynamic milieu, emerged a number of philosophers who articulated an "indigenous social philosophy" critiquing caste orthodoxy and feudal exploitation in Malabar" (38). They provided philosophical support to the peasant and workers struggles against caste discrimination and economic exploitation and embedded their radical critique in religious terms. It is important that these philosophers did not limit themselves to the realm of spiritual discourse, but also actively undertook social reform and engaged with questions

of material deprivation. One such figure was Vagbhadananda Gurudevar from north Malabar. He combined his oratorical skills and profound scholarship to organise the working people and untouchable castes. Struggles against caste discrimination and economic exploitation and couched their radical critique in religious terms. It is significant that these philosophers did not confine themselves to the realm of spiritual discourse, but also actively undertook social reform and engaged with questions of material deprivation.

Vagbhatananda founded the Atmavidyasangham (League for self or divine knowledge) in 1917, but later it was registered as a charitable society. It was a secular, intellectual and reformative organization based on epistemology, logic and rationalism of Advaita philosophy. All people irrespective of religion, caste and creed could be the members of the Sangham. It had been a major force of social change in Malabar. Atmavidya Sangham intended to manifest friendly co-existence and universal solidarity among the people without the barriers of religion, caste and creed. Vagbhatananda and Atmavidyasangham visualized a society of love, self-respect, liberty and equality and propagated the principle, 'May all the world live in peace.' Atmavidyasangham declared their motto in the pages of *Abhinava Keralam* (Modern or New Kerala). The mouthpiece of the Sangham was:

“Awake, remember the Lord Almighty,
Get up at once and fight injustice.” (Abhinava Keralam)

It is clear from this slogan that Vagbhatananda and his Sangham were against all injustices. The slogan was an inducing power in sprouting moral consciousness and virtuous principles in the minds of the people. The system and programme of the Atmavidyasangham was humanistic and liberal in its outlook. The Sangham enforced a set of rules of personal ethics to its members which were more related to the impersonal philosophy of Advaita. The important objective of the Sangham is to reform the individual and society as a whole. To conduct protest against caste system, untouchability, idol worship, rituals and ceremonies and all sectarian tendencies of religion which created social degeneration were the important agenda of the

Atmavidyasangham. The Sangham attempted to liberate people's mind from superstitions and other evil beliefs and gave importance to an ideal life based on morality.

All the Renaissance thinkers of Kerala mentioned above wanted to establish equality, justice and fraternity in society so as to make the society from exploitation and oppression. They behaved that all human beings belonged to one simple family. Therefore all the evils customs and practices their exactly in the society of Kerala was a reflection of the principle. Hence they wanted to establish a new social order which was completely free from exploitation, oppression and all other evils customs and practices for they based all their activities and social reforms on the foundations of Secularism, Democracy, Socialism, Modernisation, Neo-Vedanta and Humanism etc. They thought that though their ideals they will be able to bring about equality and justice in a multicultural and multi religious society of Kerala. Social reform movement based on the principles of truth, liberty, equality, fraternity, social justice and human rights tried to wipe out many unjust practices from the Kerala society. Renaissance leaders' activities helped to public conscious against social evil like caste system, superstitious, social injustice etc. Kerala renaissance thinkers worked base on dharma. Thus dharma becomes the inner principle which sustains or holds together the entire society.

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KIRANĀVALĪ
Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation
The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XIV.
Book III-IV
JULY – DECEMBER 2022

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram-36
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